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DEVELOPMENT OF A 13s MODEL STRATEGY FRAMEWORK IN CULTIVATING POLITE LANGUAGE PRACTICES FOR INDIGENOUS STUDENTS

Mohamad Nik Mat Pelet^{1*}, Anida Sarudin² and Nor Hani Suhaimi³

¹PhD, Senior Lecturer, Department of Malays Studies, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia, Email: nikmat@uitm.edu.my Orcid ID: 0009-0008-2899-6248

²PhD, Associate Professor, Faculty of Language and Communication, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, Perak, Malaysia, Email: anida@fbk.upsi.edu.my Orcid ID: 0000-0002-9795-8906

³M.A, Research Assistant, BMWORLD Sdn. Bhd., Bandar Sri Petaling, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Email: norhanisuhaimi@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: Mohamad Nik Mat Pelet

(nikmat@uitm.edu.my)

ABSTRACT

Politeness of language Politeness of language is an important element that needs to be mastered by every level of society, especially Malaysians, because it is highly valued to ensure the sustainability of Malaysia as a pluralistic country rich in noble character. The diversity of society also encourages the element of politeness of language to be mastered by all Malaysians to ensure that the aspects of unity and well-being in life are preserved. Indigenous children are the focus of this study because it was found that their response is limited to situations with a background of politeness of language, thus prompting efforts to develop a teaching and learning (T&L) model to increase this element in their life practices. Therefore, the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework was developed based on Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987) with a metric measurement of 13 polite strategies through five development phases: (i) identifying language politeness levels through needs analysis involving students and teachers; (ii) designing the model structure, content, and strategies; (iii) developing instructional materials and visual components; (iv) evaluating the model through expert validation and pilot testing; and (v) empowering the model through refinement and implementation planning. Thus, this model framework functions as a guide in systematic and contextual teaching and is suitable for use by teachers in the 21st century classroom. The development of the 13s model framework has obtained validity from 55 primary school teachers, 6 experts in Malay language education. In the meantime, the study also involved 50 native students to ensure that it has high reliability. The study findings show that the 13s model framework achieves good content validity of 93% (content validity coefficient >0.70) and good reliability value (Cronbach's Alpha coefficient value = 0.96). The implications of the study show that the 13s model framework can be used as a guide and support for teachers to instill the value of politeness among native students. The impact is that the cultivation of language politeness practices can be mastered by every individual regardless of background who not only has knowledge, but also attitudes, practices and appreciation related to language politeness elements.

KEYWORDS: Language Politeness, Native Students, 13s Model Framework, Teaching and Learning, Brown & Levinson (1987).

1. INTRODUCTION

Indigenous people are part of the population that originates and resides in Malaysia. The indigenous community group consists of the Orang Asli in peninsular Malaysia while, in Sarawak, they are known as other races besides Sarawak Malays such as Melanau, Iban, Kenyah, Kayan and so on (Nahar, N. et al., 2018). The same goes for the population in Sabah who consists of various indigenous communities such as Kadazan, Dusun, Bajau, Murut and so on. The background of the indigenous community consisting of various languages, cultures and customs makes their lives unique. In fact, their lifestyle has become a universal identity as a symbol of the nuanced image of Malaysia (Daud, N., & Othman, M. S., 2025). However, there are significant differences in the elements of communication between indigenous people and other community groups to the point of being misunderstood, although it is part of the uniqueness of their way of life. Politeness of language is the basis of communication which is a prerequisite for communication to describe the social order of a society Hassan, A. F. M. et al., 2020).

Therefore, the aspect of politeness of language is among the matters often discussed by academics in the development of communication elements of indigenous communities. The increasingly modern world with technological sophistication is bridging the gap between the global community and the local or indigenous community. Various information or viral issues can be accessed at any time by all levels of society, bringing positive or negative influences. Although most indigenous communities live in remote rural or inland areas (Daud, N., & Othman, M. S., 2025), the potential of the borderless environment can affect their lifestyle (Hamizi, M. A. F., & Hamzah, I. S., 2023) state that it is part of the threat in various situations, whether social, criminal or defamatory, if not handled as well as possible.

Therefore, the necessity of cultivating politeness in language in lifestyle must be developed from an early age, whether starting at home or in teaching and learning at school (Hassan, H. et al., 2021). There are various politeness strategies that can be mastered and practiced, including sincerity strategies, humility strategies, forgiveness strategies, solution strategies, opportunity strategies, appreciation and praise strategies, gratitude strategies, metaphor strategies, gentle or gentle strategies, greeting or self-introduction strategies, sense of humor strategies, greeting or reprimanding strategies and Rabbani expression strategies. Therefore, efforts to develop a

teaching and learning model framework are carried out to assist teachers, especially in implementing politeness strategies during teaching and learning sessions. The Development of the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework utilizes Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987) as a basis in forming polite language practices, thus improving the ability to communicate with a high level of politeness, especially among native students.

Indigenous students lack confidence, causing them to be limited in expressing responses to situations that require them to highlight polite language practices. This situation is influenced by various factors such as lack of exposure, lack of interaction with other community groups or insensitivity to the importance of education as per the opinion of (Daud, N., & Othman, M. S., 2025) who found that education is not a primary need among indigenous children because of their tendency to play and have fun rather than prioritizing education to gain appropriate knowledge, experience and practice. Meanwhile, Subhi, N. et al., (2016) explained that education is the best way to help empower indigenous communities in various aspects including social and economic. At the same time, this situation is also caused by environmental influences, lack of emphasis from the family, and the absence of consistent monitoring of the use of polite language, causing it to not develop well in the practices of indigenous students. As a result, it can affect the formation of students' personalities and create an effective communication gap between students and teachers, peers, and communities of various races.

No less important is the content of the educational curriculum applied in a subject that also plays an important role in cultivating the practice of language politeness among students, especially indigenous students. According to Narzaray, N. F. A., & Rus, A. K. A. M. (2023) the changes that have occurred in the school curriculum are aimed at achieving national aspirations in various aspects, including achieving unity, quality of life and the development of knowledge through various elements, including language politeness. Therefore, it is undeniable that the Ministry of Education Malaysia (KPM) is very sensitive to the elements of noble values in every subject taught in schools, however, its focus is not on strengthening language politeness compared to practicing good values that can be expressed through physical behavior alone. According to Hamizi, M. A. F., & Hamzah, I. S. (2023), the ambiguity and confusion of the implementer cause an approach in the curriculum to not be delivered effectively due to

changes and implementation competence. Therefore, with the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework that has been developed, it can be implemented in all subjects by emphasizing 13 clear, tangible and guided strategies to highlight aspects of language politeness.

In addition, although most indigenous students live in rural or remote areas, the world without borders is able to connect them with the outside world. In the era of globalization and the rapid development of communication technology, it can highlight the diversity of language use among school students, especially the influence on social media that uses abusive language, slang and code mixing that does not highlight the element of politeness (Hamzah, Z. A. Z. et al., 2011). Ultimately, this situation leads to the neglect or decline of polite language practices, especially in daily interactions between students and teachers, peers and society. As a result, the value of respect and polite manners in speech is increasingly eroded and thinned. According to Nahar, N. et al. (2018), children's communication and social relationships are vulnerable and tend to be affected by social interactions on a digital platform. As a result, politeness practices are eroded due to the channeling of negative elements that receive more attention in the media or modern technology.

Cultural and language differences are among the main issues in this study because indigenous communities have slightly different living norms from other communities. According to Yap, B. L. (1977), indigenous communities, like people, have similarities, but he explained that they have different cultures, accents, dialects and customs. Therefore, cultural and language differences cause them to be unable to express language politeness that is relevant to the dominant community in Malaysia. Therefore, identifying patterns of language politeness among indigenous students can help researchers analyze patterns or politeness strategies that they often use. Meanwhile, language politeness is the core of forming good relationships between two parties. Communication requires a person's verbal knowledge competence to express appropriate forms of interaction so that it becomes symbolic of the oral tradition that symbolizes the identity of a community group. Therefore, the identity and value of communication expressed need to be explored by identifying and analyzing the language politeness strategies used when interacting to help researchers determine the form of identity that can be marked for indigenous students, including adjusting the content of the politeness model framework that will be

produced through this study.

Perumal, T., Sinayah, M. et al. (2024) also emphasized that a crisis in communication occurs because of the diversity of a person's background so that the style of speech, choice of words and response when speaking is received either positively or negatively. This situation usually occurs when the acceptance of people around and normalize negative elements by assuming that the diversity of the speaker's background causes a person's politeness to vary. Therefore, the necessity of cultivating polite language in lifestyle must be developed from an early age, whether starting from home or in teaching and learning at school. There are various politeness strategies that can be mastered and practiced, including the sincere strategy, the humble strategy, the apology strategy, the solution strategy, the opportunity giving strategy, the appreciation and praise strategy, the gratitude strategy, the metaphorical strategy, the gentle or gentle strategy, the greeting or introduction strategy, the cleverness strategy, the greeting or reprimand strategy and the Rabbani expression strategy.

Therefore, efforts to develop a teaching and learning model framework were made to assist teachers, especially in implementing language politeness strategies during teaching and learning sessions. The development of the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework utilizes Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987) as a basis for shaping language politeness practices, thus improving the ability to communicate with a high level of language politeness, especially among native students.

This study was conducted to [i] identify and [ii] analyze the use of language politeness among indigenous students as well as to [iii] improve and [iv] shape language politeness practices through the application of the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework among indigenous students. Although this study only focused on indigenous students, the framework developed will later be tested on other study participants other than indigenous students, including teachers' perceptions with a larger proportion.

The five phases of the 13s Model Framework development are aligned with the research objectives. Phase 1 (Language Politeness Level) addresses objectives [i] identification and [ii] analysis by examining students' existing politeness practices. Phase 2 (Model Design) and Phase 3 (Model Development) address objective [iii] improvement by constructing and refining the framework. Phase 4 (Model Evaluation) and Phase 5 (Model

Empowerment) address objective [iv] by establishing and strengthening politeness practices through implementation and validation. This alignment ensures that the development process systematically achieves all research objectives.

The Development of the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework was developed through five

phases, namely Phase 1: Language Politeness Level, Phase 2: Language Politeness Model Design, Phase 3: Language Politeness Model Development, Phase 4: Language Politeness Model Evaluation and Phase 5: Language Politeness Model Empowerment. The five phases can be explained as in the following table 1.

Table 1: Model Framework Development Phase 13s.

Design Phase	Details
Phase 1 Language Politeness Level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of Target Groups • Analysis of Environment • Analysis of Driving Factors
Phase 2 Design of Language Politeness Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content planning • Design strategy • Design layout • Interface design • Navigation
Phase 3 Development of the Language Politeness Model Framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot Implementation of vector graphics • Clip animated sequences • Graphic vector background <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compilation
Phase 4 Evaluation of Language Politeness Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply • Testing • Modification
Phase 5 Empowerment of Language Politeness Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent Model Framework • Joint efforts to implement modules with NGOs in Semporna Sabah • Collaborate with MOE to empower indigenous students

In Phase 1, data were collected using (i) a needs analysis questionnaire distributed to 55 teachers and (ii) informal situational interviews with 50 indigenous students. The interviews required students to respond to specific communication scenarios to assess their use of politeness strategies. These data were used to identify existing gaps in language politeness practices and to inform the design of the model in Phase 2.

The 13 strategies contained in the Brown and Levinson Politeness Theory (1987) were used as a basis to develop the 13s Model framework. The theory emphasizes the importance of sincerity strategies, humility strategies, forgiveness strategies,

solution strategies, opportunity strategies, appreciation and praise strategies, gratitude strategies, metaphor strategies, gentle or gentle strategies, greeting or self-introduction strategies, witty strategies, greeting or reprimanding strategies and Rabbani expression strategies that need to be highlighted by each individual in a communication.

Based on figure 1, the 13s Model Framework was developed by gradually implementing each of the 13 language politeness strategies in teaching and learning. At level 1, teachers are advised to emphasize three strategies, namely sincerity, humility and expressing apologies based on the situation.

Figure 1: Framework of The Language Politeness Model 13s.

In other words, for every skill or learning content delivered in any subject, teachers need to cross-apply the elements of these three strategies as an effort to provide knowledge, form attitudes, implement practices and create an appreciation of language politeness among students. Other stages can be implemented if the teacher is satisfied with the strategies that have been implemented each time teaching and learning occurs. Ultimately, after the implementation of the four stages is complete, students can cultivate language politeness through the 13 strategies emphasized in this model framework.

1.1. Concept Of Development 13s Model Strategy Framework

The 13s strategy model is a form of model developed to shape students' characters with polite values through 13 strategies as presented in the Brown and Levinson Politeness Theory (1987). The 13 strategies in the theory are arranged according to four main levels to facilitate the implementation of teachers in schools. The four levels are also based on specific objectives such as forming knowledge at level 1, forming attitudes at level 2, forming practices at level 3 and making it an appreciation, which is practice at level 4. At each level and objective, each strategy is also emphasized in stages from easy strategies to difficult strategies such as the sincere strategy, the humble strategy and the apology strategy at level 1. This strategy is believed to be easy to master by students because it is basic in life. While the RABBANI expression strategy, greeting strategy and witty strategy at level 4 require students to first master the basic strategies such as at levels 1, 2 and 3 before mastering the strategy at level 4.

While the 13s Model Framework is grounded in Brown and Levinson's (1987) Politeness Theory, it extends the theory by operationalising abstract politeness strategies into structured, teachable components suitable for classroom implementation. Unlike the original theory, which focuses on explaining politeness behaviour, the 13s model emphasises pedagogical application by organising strategies into progressive levels (knowledge, attitude, practice, and appreciation). This approach bridges the gap between theoretical understanding and practical teaching, particularly in culturally diverse educational settings.

In the meantime, the 13s model strategy framework that was developed is not only relevant in certain subjects, but also across all subjects in schools. In other words, it can be implemented by any teacher in all subjects to help improve the morals,

attitudes and practices of students who are now very exposed to impolite practices. According to Mohsin, M. (2010) and Ramlan, N. et al., (2024), learning activities need to be well-designed and of good quality to ensure that students not only benefit but also form understanding through practice in a skill. The same is true of the opinion Austrus, E. et al., (2025) which explains that there are various steps that can be implemented in improving the capabilities of indigenous communities, either through the formation of modules that can be used as a stimulus in improving their skills. Therefore, it coincides with the development of the 13s model strategy framework that has been developed.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies on language politeness have been conducted by analyzing several elements such as politeness practices in the classroom, social media comment sections, including impoliteness practices. Therefore, several previous studies were referred to and analyzed to identify and subsequently analyze the elements of language politeness in everyday communication in society by examining the gaps to improve the framework of the model produced.

Politeness of language is the main vehicle for ensuring that elements of harmony exist in communication. Studies on politeness of language have often been discussed for a long time. Among the western scholars who have actively discussed issues related to politeness are Ervin (1972), Grice (1975), Leech (1983) and Fraser (1990). Various concepts, rules and principles and strategies have been put forward by western scholars to ensure that the politeness of language model can be strengthened in the community. According to Beden, S. (2019), politeness of language is a catalyst for the formation of a person's personality in addition to being linked to an attitude of professionalism. The aspect of politeness is often underestimated by some parties in communicating while each individual is required to be prudent in communication so as not to lose face of any party and thus avoid conflict when communicating. This aspect of politeness of language is no less important for indigenous children so that they can be trained through the implementation of the politeness model developed so that they are able to communicate with the 13 strategies of politeness principles emphasized in the Brown & Levinson Theory (1987).

A study by Ahmad, N. et al. (2020) also studied the language behavior of requests among Malay students at the Language Studies Academy UiTM Shah Alam and found that Malay students used a

clear sequence of requests in conveying language behavior of requests through the use of verbs that support the main illocution in appeasing the listener so that they do not feel that the utterance is a request in fulfilling the context of the request. A study aimed at Malay students who are synonymous with politeness culture is a study that has been widely discussed. Therefore, studies related to indigenous children also need to be strengthened because the language politeness practices practiced by the relevant community group may be different from the politeness practices of the Malay community.

This statement is supported by the findings of a study by Nasrudin, N. (2018) which explains that every individual needs to be skilled in producing language acts to express something to avoid misunderstandings that cause gaps. He added that pragmatic knowledge and language proficiency are interdependent to determine the correct language act strategy when communicating. Therefore, this study needs to be conducted because of the background of pre-native children who do not receive a perfect education and extensive experience to determine the appropriate language politeness strategy when they make requests, apologies, and so on. Pragmatic knowledge that is not specifically exposed to indigenous children needs to be emphasized and studied as in this study. The findings of this study can also answer questions related to the politeness patterns practiced by indigenous children when communicating. Finally, it will lead to quality data to help researchers develop a language politeness model framework that is suitable for indigenous children.

In addition, foreign studies, Brown (2015) found that there are two different types of politeness that can exist when communication occurs. Among them is negative politeness that exists at any time and may be uninvited, which encourages expressions of respect, restraint and avoidance. Meanwhile, positive politeness arises from long-term relationships with important people in taking their feelings into account, encouraging expressions of social, caring and accepting approaches. Examples of responses involving feelings include courtesy, wisdom, resistance, attitude, sensitivity, calmness, understanding, relationship, attitude, urbanity, different behavior, rudeness, seriousness and its effects can cause shame and humiliation. This situation clearly proves that the 13s principle emphasized in the framework of the developed model is able to produce a generation of indigenous children who are able to create positive politeness when communicating and maintain the occurrence of

expressions that encourage negative politeness, causing unwanted communication.

Meanwhile, a study by Blum-Kulka, House and Kasper (1989) on language acts in Western societies explains that pragmatics is comprehensive and cross-cultural and linguistic. In fact, Blum-Kulka *et al.* (1989) have introduced a framework that is the main guide for analyzing language acts of requests and apologies. Three components are (i) triggers (alerters); request acts (head acts); and (iii) supportive acts (supportive moves). Among others is a study by Austin, J. L. (1962) who first introduced the concept of language acts as a basic unit of communication activities between individuals that will focus on how to connect an act while speaking with the meaning to be conveyed. Searle (1976) also improved Austin's (1962) study and ideas by categorizing five types of acts, namely (i) representative, (ii) declarative, (iii) directive, (iv) commissive and (vi) expressive. He added that an utterance does not only function as speech but also acts as an intention to do something. This finding proves that the aspect of politeness does not only exist in the culture of the Malay community but it is also able to cross cultures and languages as stated by Blum-Kulka, House and Kasper (1989). Therefore, this study needs to be conducted to identify and analyze the patterns or themes of politeness in indigenous children's language to prove that it is cross-cultural and linguistic.

In addition, the very high politeness values in Malaysian society, especially the Malay community, expect the same values in other social groups to create harmony in communication, which encourages language researchers to study the phenomenon of politeness among children because the formation of these values can be formed from the very beginning. A study by Sharon, L. J. (1979) found that children tend to respect people older than them when interacting compared to people of the same age or younger. In fact, children show high politeness in speaking when they ask the listener to do something for them, while the phenomenon among indigenous children is the opposite. The difference between children from other societies and indigenous children can also be measured through pragmatics. Although indigenous children live in their own groups, their politeness can also be expressed through the culture and language that is relevant to them. Therefore, this study will later help researchers to obtain valid data on language politeness among indigenous children.

A study by Hamid, Z. and Abu, N. Z. (2013) also found that the use of correct personal pronouns

according to ethnicity is influenced by social distance and status factors, which also influence their use by children. Therefore, pronouns such as *saya-awak* which are categorized as more polite are used when interacting with people who are newly acquainted, as per the opinion of Leech, G. (1983) that increasingly polite speech is used when interacting with people who are socially distant. The same is true of the findings of the study by Ogiermann, E. (2015) which found that six-year-old children can already use the auxiliary word *boluh* in making requests to others in the context of certain situations. The differences in language used by indigenous children need to be analyzed through the pronouns used when they interact with other communities. The purpose is to determine the form or pattern of politeness when they call someone or the polite lexical used in an interaction.

Badariah et al. (2013) also suggested that the school system should be given special attention to indigenous children such as the Bajau Laut because it is the basis for this community group to change and live a better life through perfect education and positive interaction with other communities. It aims to educate them to assimilate and evolve with the environment so that their presence among other communities is well accepted and not taken lightly. Therefore, the actions of several non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Semporna, Sabah to fight for special schools for these children should be welcomed, including planning an education system that is relevant to their needs such as the use of a language politeness model that will be developed later. The same is true of a study by Liu et al. (2015) which found that education issues for indigenous children such as the Bajau Laut community are still not being addressed properly, while the role of education in fostering social cohesion is able to improve the quality of life and their interaction system is more effective and accepted in society. With the 13s model framework developed through this study, it can be implemented in the teaching and learning of indigenous children such as the Bajau Laut community.

Among others, a study by Sariyan, A. (2007) explains politeness as polite, polite, civilized, showing a noble personality and showing a sign of respect to the party with whom one communicates or chats. In fact, Ahmad et al. (2016) said politeness also includes a system of greetings, nicknames to describe civilized and polite actions. Meanwhile, Ibrahim, K. and Kamaruzaman, N. F. (2017) found that the aspect of politeness also involves various forms of communication mediums such as verbal, written and

non-verbal. This is said to be so because politeness indirectly reflects the individual's personality whether a person behaves politely or not. Therefore, the previous study discussed focuses heavily on the aspect of politeness of language when communicating to ensure that our presence is not only liked but can also have a positive impact when communicating. Therefore, studies related to the development of the 13s Language Politeness Model framework should be developed in order to produce a generation that practices politeness among indigenous children.

So clearly, the findings of previous studies prove the existence of polite language values among children through studies that focus on requests, social actions, refusals, and the use of personal pronouns. This statement is further strengthened by the opinion of Shen, Z. et al. (2023) in their study also found that the element of politeness is fundamental in a person's life because it begins to be formed from the beginning, however, it begins to erode when there is a transition or change in life. In other words, the element of politeness has been acquired initially but needs to be polished in various ways including through teaching and learning through a model framework such as this study.

Therefore, a study examining the politeness of indigenous children needs to be conducted to provide alternative variations on the perspective of children's politeness since children are the easiest group to shape through direct experience, early exposure and consistent practice through the 13s model framework developed through this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research methodology plays an important role in a study to ensure that researchers can analyze data well and discuss scientifically (Darusalarn, G., & Hussin, S., 2016). The research method used is a qualitative method by interviewing study participants. The study participants involved consisted of indigenous Bajau Laut students in Semporna, Sabah aged between 10 and 15 years old. All study participants attended one of the schools around the water village in Semporna named School X. 50 selected study participants represented three different villages around School X named KA, KB and KC. In addition, 55 respondents among teachers who teach in schools for indigenous children were also involved in this study and five content experts on the development of the 13s Model Framework from various educational institutions. In the meantime, respondents among indigenous children, namely Bajau Laut children, were also interviewed

informally based on situations that required them to state the politeness strategies they would exhibit when in certain situations that required politeness practices to be highlighted. The findings of the interviews were manually analyzed to identify the use of language effects and finally the data was used to support discussions related to the development of the 13s Model Framework. The interview protocol consisted of situational prompts designed to elicit politeness strategies. For example, students were asked how they would respond in situations such as: (i) requesting help from a teacher, (ii) apologising after making a mistake, (iii) thanking someone for assistance, and (iv) responding to a disagreement with a peer. These scenarios were adapted to the students' daily experiences to ensure contextual relevance. The responses were then analysed based on the 13 politeness strategies in the framework. The data analysis methods used in the study can be explained as in table 2.

The qualitative data were analysed using a thematic analysis approach. First, all interview responses were transcribed and reviewed repeatedly to ensure familiarity with the data. Next, open coding was conducted by identifying recurring expressions related to language politeness strategies. These codes were then grouped into categories based on the 13 politeness strategies adapted from Brown and

Levinson (1987). To enhance reliability, the coding process was reviewed by two independent researchers, and any discrepancies were discussed until consensus was achieved. This process ensured systematic categorisation and reduced researcher bias.

The development process of the 13s Model Framework took approximately six months, starting with a month-long initial survey process with teachers at the schools of indigenous students to obtain information related to the analysis of the needs for developing the 13s Model Development Framework. After completing the initial survey process, the study continued by determining the appropriate theory to align with the background of the study by conducting discussions with several experts from universities regarding the characteristics of learning framework development that are appropriate for the students' backgrounds. Next, a period of five months was for the process of developing this model framework as explained in this study including designing the framework, obtaining expert validation, interviewing indigenous teachers and students, and then pilot testing the completed model framework.

The qualitative data obtained from interviews were analysed using thematic analysis to identify patterns of politeness strategies.

Table 2: Study Instruments.

Instruments	Data Analysis Method	Details
13s Model Framework Development Needs Questionnaire	Quantitative	Descriptive Statistics (%)
13s Model Framework Reliability Questionnaire	Quantitative	Cronbach's Alpha Method The Model Framework has high reliability when the coefficient value is ≥ 0.7 (Frangkel & Wallen, 1996; Kerlinger, 1986).
13s Model Validity Expert Assessment Questionnaire	Quantitative	Content Validity = $\frac{\text{Total expert score}}{\text{Maximum score}} \times 100\%$ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. The model framework has high validity when the percentage exceeds 78% (Sidek and Jamaludin, 2005) ii. The level of mastery or high achievement exceeds 80% (Tuckman & Waheed, 1981; Abu Bakar Nordin, 1995).Keshan

The statistical methods presented in Table 2 are used specifically to determine the validity and reliability of the model framework, and not as primary data analysis techniques. Three instruments were used in this study, namely (i) the 13s Model

Framework Development Needs Questionnaire, (ii) the 13s Model Framework Validity Questionnaire and (iii) the 13s Model Reliability Questionnaire. Table 3 shows the details related to the three instruments used.

Table 3: Instrument Details.

Instruments	Details
13s Model Framework Development Needs Questionnaire	Used to determine the development needs of the 13s model framework at stage I:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Based on Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987) ii. Administered to 55 primary school teachers teaching in a school for indigenous children iii. Involved 50 level 2 students in one of the schools for indigenous children
13s Model Framework Reliability Questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used to determine the validity of the model framework. i. Adapted from the module content validity questionnaire by Sidek and Jamaludin (2005). ii. The validity of this questionnaire was adapted from three experts in the field of Malay language education using the Content Validity Index (CVI) method S-CVI value = 1.0 accepted according to the view of Polit and Beck (2006). iii. The content of the five items was assessed iv. 5-point Likert Scale Evaluation v. Involve six experts in the field of Malay language education identified
13s Model Validity Expert Assessment Questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used to determine the reliability of the model. i. Adapted from a questionnaire to assess the reliability of the module by Sidek and Jamaludin (2005). ii. The content of 30 items was assessed. iii. 5-point Likert Scale Assessment iv. The validity of this questionnaire was adapted from three experts in the field of Malay Language Education through the Content Validity Index (CVI) method S-CVI value = 1.0 accepted according to the view of Polit and Beck (2006) v. Involved 50 level 2 students in one of the indigenous children's schools after the pilot study was completed and administered

The data collection process procedure was carried out by distributing (i) the Questionnaire on the Need for Development of the 13s Model Framework to 55 teachers who teach in schools with indigenous students. The questionnaire aimed to identify and obtain information from teachers regarding the need to improve language politeness practices among indigenous students. In addition, indigenous children were also interviewed indirectly to measure the level of language politeness in their communication practices. The data findings from both sources were analyzed to determine the design of the 13s model framework produced. Then, (ii) the Questionnaire on the Validity of the 13s Model Framework was distributed to five content experts in the field of Malay Language Education to assess the reliability of the 13s model framework produced. The findings from the five experts were analyzed for the purpose of improving the content of the 13s model framework. These experts were selected based on their academic qualifications, teaching experience, and research expertise in language pedagogy and pragmatics. All experts have more than 10 years of experience in language education and have been

actively involved in curriculum development and research related to language politeness. Next, (iii) The 13s Model Framework Reliability Questionnaire was distributed to 50 native student respondents to obtain student feedback on the content of the model framework, including informal interviews regarding language politeness practices as contained in the 13s model framework. The data obtained from teachers and students were not limited to the evaluation phase, but were first utilised in Phase 1 (needs analysis) to identify existing gaps in language politeness practices. These data were subsequently used in Phase 4 and Phase 5 to evaluate and refine the effectiveness of the developed 13s Model Framework.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The following discussion details the two objectives of this study. Among them are as follows. The analysis findings from the Questionnaire on the Development Needs of the 13s Model Framework involving 55 respondents among teachers are as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: 13s Model Framework Development Requirements.

Item	Feedback (%)
Needs to develop 13s Model Framework	96%
Priority Targets	Starting at 6 years old (Preschool)
Focus Elements	Language Politeness
Priority	Practice of Language Politeness in Communication

Based on, 96% of respondents stated the need to develop a model framework related to language politeness that can be focused on preschool students who are six years old. Respondents also suggested that the framework be introduced with basic language politeness practices that students have acquired since childhood such as the strategy of apologizing. The elements chosen by respondents also involve language politeness that can be used in students' daily communication.

To strengthen the findings of the respondent analysis, based on interview findings, the researcher found that the study participants were unable to respond appropriately based on situations that required them to express polite language strategies. Table 1 shows the findings of the analysis related to the responses. Referring to table 4, only 33 study participants responded in the interviews conducted while 17 study participants only responded with a smile or shook their heads.

Table 5: Analysis Of Language Politeness Before Implementation Of The 13s Model Framework.

Numb.	Language Politeness Strategies	X School			Sum
		KA	KB	KC	
1.	Sincere Strategy	1	0	2	3
2.	Humble Strategy	0	1	4	5
3.	Forgiveness Strategy	2	0	0	2
4.	Solution Strategy	3	1	1	5
5.	Giving Opportunities Strategy	0	1	1	2
6.	Appreciation and Praise Strategy	0	0	1	1
7.	Thankfulness Strategy	2	0	2	4
8.	Figurative Strategy	0	0	0	0
9.	Gentle Strategy	0	1	1	2
10.	Greeting or Self Introduction Strategy	1	3	2	6
11.	Witty Strategy	0	0	0	0
12.	Repremanding Strategy	0	1	1	2
13.	RABANI Expression Strategy	0	1	0	1
	Sum	9	9	15	33

Table 5 shows the inability of all study participants to exhibit figurative and clever strategies in communication so that they did not give any appropriate response to describe the politeness of language that could be highlighted in the situation. Similarly, the strategy of apology, appreciation or praise and Rabhani expressions also showed that they were still limited compared to the strategy of sincerity, giving opportunities, thanking, being polite and greeting. Meanwhile, the strategy of regret and greeting or introducing oneself showed a significant level of practice among study participants. The findings of this analysis prove that knowledge about politeness strategies among study participants is still limited, affecting their attitudes and practices, making it difficult to appreciate by practicing and making it part of the culture.

Therefore, the need to develop the Language Politeness Model Framework 13s is empowered to assist teachers in particular and the Malaysian Ministry of Education in general to implement politeness strategies across all school curricula in various subject content. This effort can to some extent further improve the quality of national education in forming a CIVIL (MADANI) generation who are sensitive to the needs of polite elements throughout their lives.

After the 13-model framework was produced as shown in Figure 1, the 13s Model Framework Validity Questionnaire was distributed to five experts to validate the content of the 13s model framework that had been developed. The following discussion will detail the analysis findings as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: 13s Model Framework Reliability Questionnaire.

Item	Expert Evaluation					Total Expert Score	Maximum Score	Percent Validity (%)
	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5			
1	5	4	4	5	4	22	25	88
2	5	4	5	5	5	24	25	96
3	4	5	5	5	4	24	25	96
4	4	5	4	5	5	23	25	92
5	5	5	4	5	4	23	25	92
6	5	5	5	5	4	24	25	96
	Sum					140	150	93

Table 6 shows that the validity percentage for the 13s model framework is high at 93%, which is above the 70% level as per the opinion of Sidek and Jamaludin (2005), Abu Bakar Nordin (1995) and Tuckman and Waheed (1981) that a value of 70% for content validity is sufficient to determine that a

model can be used in teaching and learning. Therefore, to strengthen the findings of the analysis, table 7 refers to the findings of the analysis for the 13s Model Framework Reliability Questionnaire which involved 50 respondents among native level II students.

Table 7: 13s Model Validity Expert Assessment Questionnaire.

No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Cronbach's Alpha
30	.965	.966

The high Cronbach's Alpha value (0.966) indicates strong internal consistency among the items in the model framework. However, this does not necessarily imply that all politeness strategies are equally easy to master. Some strategies, such as figurative and witty strategies, may require higher cognitive and linguistic competence, as reflected in the lower initial responses among students. Therefore, while the model demonstrates strong reliability overall, certain strategies may require additional instructional emphasis and scaffolding.

According to Frangkel and Wallen (1996) and Kerlinger (1986), satisfactory reliability refers to a coefficient value ≥ 0.7 . Therefore, the findings in table 7 show that the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient value is .966, which shows that the 13s Model is suitable for use as a support for teachers to teach by emphasizing the element of politeness of language.

To strengthen discussions regarding the reliability of the 13s model framework developed, the 13s

Language Politeness Model Framework that was developed has gone through a pilot process on the same study participants by implementing the model framework in all teaching and learning subjects taught at school X. At this stage, teachers are given the freedom to use existing resources such as pictures, animations or written dialogues to implement the 13 language politeness strategies. This method provides teachers with the opportunity to explore more content that is thought to be appropriate for the skills being taught by aligning it with the 13 strategies contained in the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework.

After this implementation process was completed in approximately two months, there was an improvement compared to the situation before the 13s Model Framework was introduced. Study participants were interviewed with the same interview questions and asked to respond to the situations presented.

Figure 2. 13s Model Framework Implementation Data.

Figure 2 shows an increase in 13s practices among study participants compared to only 33 people

responding previously.

Table 8: Analysis Of Language Politeness After Implementation Of The 13s Model Framework.

Numb.	Language Politeness Strategies	X School			Sum.
		KA	KB	KC	
1.	Sincere Strategy	1	1	2	4
2.	Humble Strategy	2	1	2	5
3.	Forgiveness Strategy	2	1	2	5
4.	Solution Strategy	2	1	1	4
5.	Giving Opportunities Strategy	0	1	1	2
6.	Appreciation and Praise Strategy	1	1	1	3
7.	Thankfulness Strategy	2	1	2	5
8.	Figurative Strategy	1	1	1	3
9.	Gentle Strategy	1	1	1	3
10.	Greeting or Self Introduction Strategy	1	3	2	6
11.	Witty Strategy	1	1	1	3
12.	Repremanding Strategy	1	1	1	3
13.	RABANI Expression Strategy	0	1	0	1
	Sum.	15	15	17	47

Table 8 shows the increase in the number of students who responded to situations that required them to express aspects of language politeness. After the implementation of the 13s Model Framework, 47 students gave clear and significant responses related to politeness strategies as emphasized in the Brown and Levinson Politeness Theory (1987). This increase is enough to prove that the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework applied in teacher training is able to increase knowledge, attitude formation, strategy practice and subsequently appreciation, which ultimately culturally cultivates language politeness in society regardless of background.

The 13s Language Politeness Model Framework can be patented as a form of teaching and learning model that can be implemented in all subjects in schools by relating situations or circumstances that require politeness strategies to the skills found in a given subject being taught. According to Zainor, N. S. et al., (2025), teachers need to be creative by highlighting elements of language politeness and at the same time the skills taught become the backbone of teaching and learning. For example, when a mathematics teacher teaches calculation skills for division operations, the teacher can insert a situation of division operations into the students' environment and encourage appropriate behavior or responses for them to highlight through language politeness strategies. This delivery method not only strengthens students' understanding of division operations, but at the same time there is an element of added value in students' skills, namely language politeness strategies (Subhi, N. et al., 2016).

Among other things, the significant changes in the responses of the study participants prove that the element of politeness needs to be taught consistently

in various subjects through an organized, interesting and gradual implementation as per the efficient and comprehensive 13 model strategy framework. According to Pelet, M. N. M. et al. (2025) and Yaacob, Z. (2020), interesting teaching is not only influenced by the techniques, teaching aids and methods used by the teacher, but the content or elements of a skill being taught also need to be processed so that it becomes attractive to students to be consistent and subsequently master the elements or skills being taught as contained in the 13s model. Then with the high level of mastery as in figure 2 and table 2 clearly proves that their appreciation of the element of politeness can be achieved at level 4 by appreciating the practice of politeness. According to Mahamod, Z. et al. (2020), the level of understanding, appreciation and practice proves that a person's identity can be formed through various methods including teaching and learning in school (Marganingsih, M. et al., 2022).

Therefore, the impact of the efforts to develop the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework, the researchers have produced an innovation kit called the 13s e-Module which will be used as a guide and structured material to implement teaching and learning based on the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework in the future. Both of these products are later proposed to be used comprehensively and not only focused on native students because the elements included in the 13s Language Politeness Model Framework and the innovation module are relevant and suitable for all levels in schools. Halimi, N., & Rawian, R. (2025) explains that having a framework as a basis can help someone determine the form of information that will be integrated for processing and become the core of an action. Similarly, the 13s model framework produced through this study can

be used as a reference for individuals who need to improve the elements of politeness in language.

This study has several limitations. First, the sample is limited to one indigenous community, which may affect the generalisability of the findings. Second, the duration of implementation was relatively short (two months), which may not fully capture long-term behavioural changes. Third, the reliance on qualitative interviews and self-reported responses may introduce subjectivity. Future studies should incorporate longitudinal designs and mixed-method approaches to strengthen the findings.

5. CONCLUSION

The development of a teaching model framework such as the 13s Model Framework is a form of innovation that needs to be developed by producing an innovation kit or module as a step to empower teacher teaching and learning by emphasizing the elements contained in the 13s model. The 13s Model Framework, which was developed systematically and comprehensively, is hoped to help diversify teachers' teaching and learning methods in conveying skills by emphasizing language politeness strategies in order to produce knowledgeable and civilized students.

In other words, the politeness aspect in an individual can be developed in various ways, including by developing a strategic framework like this to ensure that language behavior can be formed with polite values. According to Austrus, E. et al. (2025), a person's language behavior reflects polite values that can be expressed through certain lexical items that give a positive or negative image. In the meantime, through the development of this framework, it also proves that polite values are not only relevant to a country but also across other countries that can be adapted through this developed framework.

According to Narzaray, N. F. A., & Rus, A. K. A. M. (2023), every country has a culture that has been practiced and accepted by its community groups, but the element of politeness is not much different from one country to another because the aspect of politeness involves human nature and tolerance as emphasized in the 13s strategic framework that has been developed. The opinion of Ramlan, N. et al. (2024), also explains that attitude is part of the constraints of an individual, especially students, in mastering politeness practices because factors are easily influenced by the environment. Then, with the existence of this 13s strategic framework, it can be formed by communicating in various situations

using language elements and positive behavior (Hamizi, M. A. F., & Hamzah, I. S., 2023).

Future research should expand the implementation of the 13s Model Framework to other indigenous communities in Malaysia, such as the Orang Asli in Peninsular Malaysia and indigenous groups in Sarawak. Comparative studies across different cultural and linguistic contexts would help determine the adaptability and scalability of the framework. In addition, further testing involving urban and mixed-background students would strengthen the generalisability of the model.

In conclusion, the 13S Model framework, which emphasizes aspects of language politeness, provides a holistic foundation in understanding and shaping communication practices that are appropriate for the context of indigenous children. Through the application of the elements in the 13s Model, the use of polite, civilized and empathetic language not only functions as a medium for conveying information, but also acts as a vehicle for preserving cultural values, community identity and harmonious social relationships. Language politeness in this context helps ensure that interactions between educators, researchers or outside communities with indigenous children occur in a way that respects cultural sensitivity, living conditions and local value systems. In addition, the 13s Model framework also emphasizes that language politeness towards indigenous children should be seen as a long-term educational and empowerment process. Polite language practices can support the emotional development, self-confidence and identity building of children, while encouraging their active participation in the learning process and social interaction. Therefore, the 13s Model is not only relevant as an academic analytical framework, but also as a practical guide in formulating policies, educational modules and social interventions that are more inclusive, culturally sensitive and based on the well-being of indigenous children.

This framework that has been developed is also expected to be used as a teaching model that is applied at all levels of schools, whether primary or secondary. The reason is to ensure that aspects of politeness among students can be formed from a young age. At the same time, this model can also be practiced at the higher education level to ensure the continuity of aspects of language politeness among future generations who will lead the country not only with knowledge and experience but also with universal polite values.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

is a Senior Lecturer at Academy of Language Studies Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia (UiTM). He was appointed lecturer in the university in 2022 and went on to pursue her graduate studies in Malay Language education at the Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Selangor, Malaysi. He is passionate about raising the quality of teaching and learning of students and their development in the schools and in the higher education settings. Dr. Mohamad Nik Mat's research interests lie in the teacher and teacher education, Malay grammer, higher education, 21st Century teaching and learning, school-based assessment, classroom research, and pragmatic practices and their education. His can be contacted at email: nikmat@uitm.edu.my (ORCID iD: 0009-0008-2899-6248)</p>	
is a Associate Professor in Malay Linguistic and a Senior Lecturer from the Faculty of Language and Communication, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, Tanjung Malim, Perak, Malaysia. She research focuses on pragmatic, semantic, corpus and Malay langauge education. She can be contacted at email: anida@fbk.upsi.edu.my (ORCID iD: 0000-0002-9795-8906)</p>	
received Master degree in Language Applied in Malay Langauge from Academy of Language Studies Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia (UiTM). She is currently a Malay Teacher at BMWORLD Sdn. Bhd, Kuala Lumpur. During studies her publication topics including pragmatic, indigenous education and educational courses. She can be contacted at email: norhanisuhaimi@gmail.com</p>	